

Achieving a 155× Speedup in a LiDAR Data Processing Pipeline

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ABSTRACT

We present a case study of systematically optimizing a real-world, multi-stage data processing pipeline for high-resolution LiDAR road condition assessment. The original system, grown over more than a decade, required weeks of computation for a typical measurement campaign covering a 10 km road network, processing approx. 200 GB of raw data. Our contribution is the end-to-end optimization of a heterogeneous, production pipeline through a combination of hardware consolidation (from a distributed eight-server architecture to a single high-performance node), elimination of intermediate file I/O through stream processing, migration from heterogeneous runtimes (MATLAB, Python, C++) to a single codebase in managed C# code, and pervasive SIMD vectorization and parallelization. The key enabler was a continuous, measurement-driven methodology: automated benchmarks tracked per-commit performance across reference datasets, allowing us to systematically identify and eliminate the dominant bottleneck at each stage of the project. We achieved a **155× end-to-end speedup**, enabling the pipeline to process data faster than it is recorded. We do not claim novel algorithms; rather, we demonstrate that disciplined engineering, including profiling, architectural simplification, and exploitation of modern hardware capabilities, can yield order-of-magnitude improvements in real-world, legacy data processing systems.

Keywords: Software optimization — LiDAR processing — SIMD vectorization — stream processing — road condition assessment — managed code performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Road infrastructure is among the most valuable public assets in any country. In Switzerland alone, the road network spans approximately 84,000 km. Regular condition assessment is essential for efficient maintenance planning, yet the data volumes produced by modern measurement vehicles create a severe computational bottleneck.

Our measurement vehicle, the Integrated Road Information System (IRIS, Figure 1) operated by IMP Bautest AG (12), is equipped with a Fraunhofer PPS+ pavement profile scanner, a Fraunhofer CPS clearance profile scanner, a Ladybug 5 panoramic camera, four machine vision cameras, two macro texture scanners, and a high-precision GNSS/IMU positioning system. During operation at typical road speeds, the system generates approximately 20 GB/km data. A full measurement campaign can produce terabytes of data that must be processed through a complex, multi-stage pipeline to extract road condition indicators such as longitudinal

Figure 1. The IRIS measurement vehicle. The roof-mounted equipment includes cameras, a road surface LiDAR, and GNSS equipment; the macro texture scanners are mounted to the bottom of the vehicle.

and transverse evenness, cracking, texture depth, and georeferenced imagery.

Prior to our work, this processing pipeline, which evolved over more than a decade, required *weeks* of computation for a full campaign. Data recording was distributed across eight servers inside the measurement vehicle, and data processing was done on up to four on-premises servers and involved a heterogeneous mix of C#, C++, MATLAB, and Python components communicating primarily through intermediate files. These processing delays meant that data quality issues could only be identified well after the measurement, limiting the ability to react during a campaign.

In this paper we describe a systematic approach that achieved a $155\times$ end-to-end speedup, enabling the pipeline to complete processing faster than data is recorded. For a representative reference dataset (a short urban measurement of approximately 0.5 km at low speed, recording duration 115 seconds), processing time dropped from over 184 minutes to 65 seconds. We used reference datasets of varying length and recording conditions for continuous benchmarking throughout the project, and report detailed results for the primary reference dataset here.

2. RELATED WORK

Mobile mapping systems and their data processing requirements have been surveyed by Elhashash et al. (7), who note that the computational demands of multi-sensor platforms remain a significant challenge.

On the algorithmic level, significant work has focused on accelerating individual LiDAR processing steps. For example, Hu et al. (9) proposed scan-line-based ground filtering of urban LiDAR point clouds with GPU acceleration, demonstrating significant speedups for individual filter operations. Rusu et al. (19) introduced the Statistical Outlier Removal (SOR) filter for 3D point clouds, a widely adopted approach for noise removal in robot perception. Pajarola (17) introduced stream-processing paradigms for point cloud data, demonstrating that streaming can reduce memory requirements and improve throughput for large datasets.

These works share a common characteristic: they optimize *individual* algorithms or processing steps in isolation. In contrast, real-world data processing pipelines consist of dozens of interdependent stages spanning data parsing, interpolation, image generation, statistical analysis, database operations, and report generation. The bottleneck in such systems is often not a single algorithm, but the accumulated overhead of file-based intermediate storage, heterogeneous runtime environments, process startup costs, and serial execution patterns. Stream processing architectures such as Apache Flink (4) address similar challenges in distributed sys-

tems by replacing batch-oriented file exchange with continuous data flows; we apply analogous principles within a single-machine, shared-memory setting.

The challenge of modernizing legacy software systems has been studied extensively in software engineering. Assunção et al. (1) provide a recent survey of contemporary strategies for legacy system modernization.

Hundt (11) provided a controlled comparison of C++, Java, Go, and Scala on identical algorithms, finding that idiomatic managed-language code can approach native performance after optimization, though language-specific tuning remains important. Modern managed runtimes such as .NET have narrowed the performance gap with native code through JIT compilation, hardware intrinsics, and memory-efficient APIs (22).

The importance of measurement-driven optimization has been recognized since Knuth’s observation that “premature optimization is the root of all evil”; systematic profiling tools enable developers to direct effort to the actual bottlenecks. The role of continuous profiling in guiding optimization effort has been demonstrated in domains ranging from compiler optimization (6) to streaming application tuning (14) and HPC workloads (2).

Our contribution differs from prior work in two ways. First, we address the end-to-end optimization of a complete, production pipeline rather than isolated algorithms. Second, our approach is explicitly measurement-driven: automated, per-commit benchmarking on reference datasets provides the feedback loop that directs optimization effort to the actual bottlenecks at each stage of the project. We demonstrate that this disciplined engineering approach can yield speedups comparable to those reported for individual GPU-accelerated kernels, but across an entire, heterogeneous processing chain.

3. HARDWARE CONSOLIDATION

The original IRIS system distributed acquisition across eight servers, connected via a 10 Gbit/s Ethernet switch. These servers ranged from Intel Core2 E7600 systems from 2009 to Intel i7-8700 machines from 2017, with heterogeneous RAM configurations and HDD-based storage. Each server was dedicated to a specific subsystem: one for each camera pair, one for each LiDAR scanner, one for the positioning system, and so on. This distributed architecture, while functional, imposed several performance limitations.

Data transfer overhead. Raw PPS+ scanner data (5–20 GB/km) had to be transferred between servers for processing. For a 100 km measurement at urban density, this amounts to terabytes of data that had to traverse

Table 1. Hardware comparison between the legacy distributed system (8 servers, cumulative) and the new consolidated server.

Component	Legacy (8 srv.)	New (1 srv.)
CPU cores (phys.)	34	48
Logical threads	58	96
RAM	68 GB	256 GB
Storage	4 TB HDD	8 TB NVMe
Storage BW	≈ 0.3 GB/s	≈ 7 GB/s

the internal network before processing could begin, a transfer that alone could take hours.

Time synchronization complexity. At highway speeds, a timing error of just one millisecond between two sensors corresponds to a spatial offset of over two centimeters, an order of magnitude over the system’s measurement resolution. The original system maintained sub-millisecond time synchronization via individual Meinberg GPS clock cards (15), a technically demanding arrangement. Custom analog-to-optical converter PCBs distributed pulse-per-second signals from the GPS clock to the LiDAR scanners via fiber optic links; understanding and migrating these custom boards was one of the challenges.

Redundant computation. Several pipeline stages independently read and parsed the same files (e.g. trajectories), because no shared memory existed between the stages.

We consolidated all computation onto a single server, whose specifications are summarized alongside the legacy system in Table 1. The new AMD EPYC 7643-based system provides approximately $11\times$ the single-threaded performance of the strongest legacy server (the PPS+ processing machine) as measured by industry benchmarks. More importantly, the 48 physical cores (96 threads), 256 GB of DDR4-3200 ECC RAM, and NVMe SSD storage with 7 GB/s sequential bandwidth provide the foundation for the architecture described in subsequent sections. The hardware was specifically chosen to provide several high-bandwidth interfaces.

The sensors now connect directly to this single server: the LiDAR scanners via fiber optic, the panoramic camera via USB 3, the machine vision cameras and the positioning system via Ethernet. A single Meinberg GPS180PEX PCIe clock card (15) provides accurate timing, even if timing accuracy is not critical anymore. The system architecture before and after consolidation is shown in Figure 2 and Figure 3.

Beyond performance, consolidation simplified operations. The previous system required coordinated startup of eight machines and verification of network links and

clock synchronization before each measurement. Diagnosing issues in the field, often 100–200 km from the laboratory, required familiarity with a heterogeneous hardware landscape. The consolidated system is easier to maintain and diagnose, and its single time reference eliminates the synchronization challenge entirely.

4. MEASUREMENT-DRIVEN OPTIMIZATION

A prerequisite for systematic performance optimization are reliable, reproducible measurements. Without knowing which pipeline stage dominates runtime, optimization effort risks being misdirected. This concern is particularly acute in a pipeline with over a dozen stages.

We developed a hierarchical timing and memory profiling framework that instruments every pipeline stage. Each processing step is wrapped in a measurement scope that records wall-clock time and samples peak process memory at 1 Hz intervals. Results are structured hierarchically (stages contain sub-stages), and written to JSON files annotated with the Git commit hash and a timestamp. An analysis script reads these files and generates stacked area charts showing per-stage runtime evolution across all commits.

This profiling framework was integrated into our continuous integration (CI) system. On every merge to the main branch, the full pipeline is executed on four reference datasets of varying length and sensor configurations, and the resulting timing data is committed to the repository. This provides an unbroken time series of per-commit performance data, enabling immediate identification of regressions and quantification of each optimization’s impact.

An important architectural decision was to run pipeline stages *sequentially* rather than overlapping multiple stages in parallel. While overlapping stages could theoretically improve throughput, running them sequentially allows precise accounting of each stage’s memory consumption and execution time. If multiple stages ran concurrently, their memory footprints, I/O loads, and garbage collection pauses would interact in complex ways, making it nearly impossible to attribute resource usage to individual stages. The sequential approach was essential for our profiling-driven methodology: each stage’s contribution to overall runtime is clearly measurable and directly actionable. Within a stage, however, parallelism is fully exploited.

Figure 4 shows the stacked area chart for the primary reference dataset. This visualization proved indispensable for directing optimization effort. Early in the project, topographic image generation dominated at over 7,000 seconds; once that was reduced, the LiDAR data reader became the next bottleneck, followed by lon-

Figure 2. Original eight-server distributed architecture. Each sensor connects to a dedicated server; all servers communicate via a fiber-optic switch.

itudinal profile analysis. At each stage, the chart immediately reveals the next most impactful target, and re-annotated regressions trigger investigation before further progress is made. We used traditional sampling profilers to optimize individual stages.

5. PROCESSING PIPELINE AND DATA FLOW

The data processing pipeline transforms raw sensor data into road condition indicators stored in a PostgreSQL/PostGIS database. Figure 5 depicts the overall data flow through the processing stages.

The pipeline was originally implemented as a sequential chain of largely independent programs. Components were written in C# (.NET Framework), C++ (native DLLs and external executables), MATLAB (compiled to standalone executables requiring the MATLAB Compiler Runtime (21)), and Python scripts. Data exchange between stages was almost entirely file-based: the LiDAR scanner reader produced intermediate data files consuming 10–40 GB/km of temporary storage, which downstream stages then re-read. Point cloud processing relied on a separate, third-party executable, and panoramic image generation invoked Python scripts, calling the Hugin (10) panoramic stitching toolkit.

Most stages ran sequentially with no parallelism, and several stages redundantly parsed the same large input files. For example, the trajectory file was loaded repeatedly by independent pipeline stages. The initial end-to-end processing time for the primary reference dataset was 184 minutes on the original hardware.

Figure 3. Consolidated single-server architecture. All sensors connect directly to one machine, eliminating network transfers and time synchronization complexity.

6. ARCHITECTURAL TRANSFORMATION: FROM FILES TO STREAMS

6.1. Scanner Data Streaming

The single most impactful category of optimization was the elimination of intermediate file I/O, replacing it with in-memory stream processing.

Originally, the LiDAR scanner reader (a C++ library provided by Fraunhofer IPM), was integrated via intermediate index and data files that consumed 10–40 GB/km of temporary storage and required a separate read pass by every downstream consumer. This write-read cycle alone accounted for a large fraction of total processing time, as it was fundamentally I/O-bound.

We redesigned the interface between the C++ library and the managed C# pipeline to use callbacks: instead of writing files, the C++ library invokes managed delegates for each extracted profile. Profiles are delivered directly into memory without serialization, and are immediately dispatched to concurrent consumer queues. This eliminated the index file generation pass, the temporary storage requirement (saving 10–40 GB/km of disk space), and the separate file-reading pass in all downstream consumers.

The 2D profiles (surface topography cross-sections used for imaging) and 3D profiles (point clouds used for longitudinal and transverse analysis) are streamed through separate data flows, allowing the scanner reader and downstream processing to operate concurrently rather than sequentially. Outliers are filtered, imputation of missing data points, and transformations into a global coordinate system. We optimized the point filtering which resulted in a more pleasing look of the surface images (Figure 6).

Figure 4. The per-stage processing time for the primary reference dataset over the project duration (May 2024–January 2025), zoomed to 2,000s to show later optimizations. Each color band represents a code section. Green annotations mark commits that reduced runtime; red annotations mark regressions. This chart guided the optimization efforts in this project, and reveals how the dominant bottleneck shifts over time.

The 2D and 3D streams are joined back together into a single stream after these processing steps. Memory consumption was reduced to approximately half of the original through compacted data formats (from 33 to 17 bytes per 2D point, and from 23 to 9 bytes per 3D point). We keep 3D profiles in memory, to avoid re-reading data as they are used by multiple processing steps. The 256 GB of available RAM provides headroom for continuous measurement runs of up to two hours.

6.2. Trajectory Parsing

The GNSS/IMU positioning system records trajectory data at 200 Hz in a text-based format, producing files on the order of a gigabyte for a typical measurement. In the original pipeline, this file was re-read and re-parsed independently by multiple pipeline stages.

We reimplemented the parser in managed C# with two key optimizations. First, the file is parsed once and the resulting trajectory is shared across all pipeline stages via in-memory references. Second, parsing itself is parallelized across multiple threads. The challenge with parallel text file parsing is that line boundaries are not known a priori: to split the file into chunks for par-

allel processing, each thread must scan forward from its assigned byte offset to find the next complete line boundary. We handle this by having each thread skip the partial line at the beginning of its chunk, while the preceding thread processes the partial line at the end of its chunk. This approach scales well to the available core count while correctly handling varying line lengths.

With these changes, the trajectory file is parsed in approximately one second, and a separate trajectory-splitting preprocessing step that was previously required to break the file into smaller segments is eliminated entirely. We order the entries in memory to allow binary searches, and perform short-range linear searches for (almost) sequential queries.

7. RUNTIME MIGRATION

7.1. MATLAB Removal

The longitudinal analysis stage, which computes evenness indicators, longitudinal profiles, and waveband decomposition, was originally implemented in MATLAB and compiled to a standalone executable requiring the

Figure 5. Data flow through the processing pipeline. Dashed arrows indicate trajectory data shared across stages for georeferencing. Results are stored in a PostgreSQL/PostGIS database and as output files (panoramas, topographic images, point clouds, reports).

Figure 6. Surface image produced by the original (*left*) and optimized (*right*) processing pipelines. The original pipeline applied no point splat filtering, resulting in grainy images. The optimized pipeline added proper filtering, and tuned the outlier filter to avoid artifacts in high-reflectance regions, such as road markings.

MATLAB Compiler Runtime (21). This architecture imposed several severe performance penalties.

Each invocation incurred a multi-second startup penalty for the MATLAB Runtime initialization. Data was serialized to intermediate text files, the MATLAB process started, and results read back, creating a full I/O round-trip for every measurement segment. The MATLAB process did not share memory with the rest of the pipeline, so large files such as the trajectory were loaded independently. And MATLAB’s process model made fine-grained parallelization across the many available CPU cores impractical (16).

We re-implemented all algorithms in C#, including longitudinal profile extraction, FFT-based frequency analysis, Power Spectral Density computation, frequency-band smoothing filters, linear regression for profile alignment, and a four-meter straightedge simulation. Each function was validated against the MATLAB reference output with per-function tolerance thresholds via unit tests.

With the MATLAB runtime eliminated, the longitudinal analysis stage now runs as part of the same process as the rest of the pipeline, sharing trajectory data in memory and benefiting from vectorization and parallelization (see §8).

7.2. Python and External Tool Removal

Panoramic image generation for a web-based annotation tool was previously implemented as a Python script calling Hugin (10), an open-source panoramic photo stitching toolkit. The pipeline used Hugin’s *nona* reprojection tool to convert equirectangular panoramic images to cube-face projections, followed by a Python tiling script that split each face into thousands of small tile files across multiple zoom levels.

This tile-based approach produced approximately 1,500–2,000 files per panoramic image. For a measurement campaign with 10,000 panoramic images, this amounts to 15–20 million small files. Managing this volume of small files creates severe overhead: on a typical network file system with 1 ms per-file latency, merely *opening* 20 million files takes 5 hours. The small average file size of a few kilobytes means that file system metadata operations dominate the actual data transfer. In practice, specially formatted disk partitions with small allocation units were used to avoid wasting disk space.

We reimplemented the panoramic generator in C#, now producing only 7 files per panoramic image instead of thousands: six cube-face JPEG images (one per face, containing all zoom levels as a power-of-two mipmap pyramid) plus one JSON metadata file with an embedded base64 thumbnail. The Pannellum (18) web viewer was configured to consume this format directly. This represents a 99.5% reduction in file count while preserving the same visual quality and zoom capability, and eliminates the Python and Hugin runtime dependencies. Each panoramic image is processed independently, enabling straightforward parallelization across all available CPU cores.

Similarly, hillshading (previously computed by the SAGA GIS (5) external tool) and image debayering (previously OpenCV (3)) were both reimplemented in C#. We used the reimplementation of these algorithms as an opportunity to improve the visual quality of the hillshading (Figure 7). For image encoding, we switched to the Windows Imaging Component (WIC), which provides hardware-accelerated JPEG and PNG encoding using SIMD instructions internally. It also enabled parallel image generation without synchronization overhead.

8. SIMD VECTORIZATION AND HIGH-PERFORMANCE MANAGED CODE

A recurring theme in our optimization work was that managed C# code, when written with care for data layout and vectorization, would easily exceed the performance of the original native C++ implementations. This section describes the techniques we applied.

8.1. Hardware Intrinsic and Platform-Adaptive Vectorization

Modern .NET provides two complementary SIMD programming models: a cross-platform vector API that automatically uses the best available instruction set, and explicit hardware intrinsics for SSE, AVX2, and AVX-512 instructions. We used both throughout the pipeline, choosing the appropriate level based on the operation.

One of the most frequently called numerical routine in the pipeline is linear interpolation, used e.g. for georeferencing every scanner profile against the trajectory. For each of the millions of 2D and 3D profiles, the interpolation kernel computes position, heading, and elevation values at the profile’s timestamp. We implemented this using AVX2 and AVX-512 intrinsics that process 8 or 16 single-precision floating-point values per instruction. The kernel computes a vector of consecutive interpolated values in a single iteration, converts them to the target format, and writes the result directly into the output buffer. A scalar fallback handles the remaining elements and platforms without AVX2 support. This pattern is applied to all bulk interpolation operations, including heading interpolation with proper angular wrap-around handling.

For image processing operations (geometric transformations, inpainting, gamma correction, debayering of Bayer RGGB raw camera data, and hillshading gradient computation) and point cloud processing, we used the platform-adaptive vector API, which automatically selects the widest available SIMD instruction set (128-bit SSE through 512-bit AVX-512) at runtime.

8.2. Allocation Avoidance and Memory Efficiency

On a many-core system processing data in parallel, garbage collection pauses can affect all threads simultaneously and can become a bottleneck. We avoid this problem by systematically reducing GC pressure through several techniques.

Temporary buffers for interpolation, image processing, and profile data are rented from a shared pool rather than allocated on the heap, and returned after use. This pattern is particularly impactful for the image generation stage, where each of the hundreds of images requires multi-megabyte temporary buffers. Small, frequently-instantiated data structures (such as per-point records in the point cloud pipeline) were changed from heap-allocated reference types to stack-allocated value types, eliminating GC tracking entirely. We reduced the memory footprint of many data structures by classic techniques like bit-packing: Outlier masks, previously stored as arrays of booleans (1 byte each), were changed to

Figure 7. Hillshaded depth image produced by the original (*left*) and optimized (*right*) processing pipelines. In the original single-channel image, gradients orthogonal to the illumination direction are invisible. The optimized pipeline employs multiple subtly colored light sources to reveal depth details across all orientations, and uses significantly larger filter kernels to capture low-frequency surface variations.

bit arrays (1 bit each), reducing memory consumption eightfold.

We also configured the runtime’s garbage collector for server workloads, using per-core collection heaps and concurrent collection. This proved essential: the default configuration, designed for interactive desktop applications, created severe contention under our parallel workloads.

During profiling, we identified a performance issue in the .NET runtime’s own JIT profiling counters. We contributed a fix upstream to the .NET runtime (8), illustrating that even the runtime itself benefits from a profiling-driven optimization methodology.

8.3. *Managed vs. Native: A Practical Observation*

An observation from our project is that managed C# implementations, when written with attention to data layout and vectorization, achieved better performance than the original native C++ and MATLAB code in our specific use cases. The point cloud transformation (see §9) dropped from over 30 minutes to under one minute, primarily due to algorithmic improvements (batched transformation matrices) that were easier to express and iterate on in managed code. The scanner data consumer pipeline in C# processes profiles faster than the C++ producer can extract them, making the native library the bottleneck. We ported several aspects of the C++ producer to C#, to alleviate the problem. The newest version of the scanner reader by the original sensor manufacturer, also in C++, proved *slower* than our managed version, suggesting that algorithm and architecture design are at least as important as language choice for this class of workload.

We do not claim that managed code is inherently faster than native code; our results reflect the specific combination of algorithm redesign, hardware-intrinsic vectorization, and reduced I/O that the managed rewrite enabled. Modern managed runtimes contain JIT compiler with auto-vectorization, bounds-check elimination for safe array access patterns, and allocation-free

APIs that make it practical to write high-performance code without sacrificing safety or developer productivity.

9. POINT CLOUD PROCESSING

Point cloud processing is one of the most computationally intensive stages. The CPS LiDAR scanner produces millions of 3D points per measurement segment that must be transformed from the scanner’s local coordinate system to georeferenced world coordinates, filtered for outliers, and compressed to the LAZ format (13) for delivery and visualization in tools such as Potree (20).

Point cloud processing for both the surface (PPS+) and corridor (CPS) scanners was fundamentally rearchitected from a multi-pass file-based approach to a single-pass streaming pipeline. Previously, a third-party native executable performed coordinate transformation and wrote uncompressed intermediate point clouds consuming 6–25 GB/km of temporary storage, followed by a separate LAZ compression step. We replaced this with a managed C# implementation that transforms, filters, and compresses points in a single streaming pass. Each raw 3D point arriving via the callback interface from the scanner library is transformed, filtered for outliers, and written directly to a LAZ file, all without materializing the intermediate, uncompressed point cloud on disk. This eliminated multiple gigabytes of temporary I/O per measurement and removed an entire pipeline stage.

Each raw 3D point from the scanner consists of three spatial coordinates (x, y, z) in the scanner’s local frame, an intensity value, and a timestamp. We used compact in-memory representations (9 bytes per PPS+ point, 24 bytes per CPS point), stored in contiguous arrays for cache-friendly access.

Georeferencing each point requires applying a rigid-body transformation (rotation + translation) derived from the vehicle’s trajectory at the point’s timestamp. We exploited the observation that points within a short time window (a “section” of approximately 1 meter of

road) share nearly identical transformations, with differences usually smaller than machine precision. By computing one transformation matrix per section and applying it to all points in that section, we amortize the cost of trajectory interpolation across hundreds or thousands of points.

After transformation, outlier points (noise from reflections, sensor artifacts, etc.) are removed using a grid-based density filter. The transformed point cloud is partitioned into a 3D grid, and cells containing fewer than a configurable threshold of points are discarded. This approach is more efficient than the commonly used Statistical Outlier Removal (SOR) filter (19) for our application, as it avoids the $O(n \log n)$ nearest-neighbor search and operates in $O(n)$ time in two passes through the point data. The grid partitioning and filtering are parallelized across sections of the point cloud.

With these optimizations, point cloud processing dropped from over 30 minutes to under one minute for the reference dataset.

10. PARALLELIZATION

Parallelization was applied at multiple levels, guided by the profiling data from the timing framework. Many pipeline stages are embarrassingly parallel: topographic images for different road sections, cross-profile report images, panoramic tile generation, and camera image processing can all proceed independently. For these stages, we applied data-parallel decomposition across all available CPU cores. The 48-core processor provides substantial parallel capacity, and the profiling data confirmed that most stages scale well to this core count.

As mentioned before, we execute pipeline stages *sequentially* rather than overlapping multiple stages in parallel. The sequential execution of the pipeline stages is helpful while performing performance tuning. A production deployment can use overlapping to increase CPU utilization further, but in our case this was not deemed necessary. Only for batch processing of extremely large campaigns do we instantiate multiple instances of the entire pipeline to maximize CPU utilization.

11. RESULTS

Table 2 shows the per-stage timing breakdown for the primary reference dataset (a 0.5 km urban measurement at approximately 4–5 m/s, recording duration 115 s). The “Original” column shows timings measured on a close approximation of the original servers; the “Optimized” column shows timings on the new server.

The total processing time of 71.4 seconds is well below the 115-second recording duration, confirming that the

Table 2. Per-stage processing times for the primary reference dataset (0.5 km, 115 s recording). Speedup reflects hardware, architecture, and code optimization combined.

Stage	Orig. (min)	Opt. (min)	Speedup
Pt. Cloud Processing	79.83	0.20	399×
Topo. Imaging	69.85	0.14	499×
Transverse Analyses	14.55	0.04	364×
IAPS Preprocessing [†]	13.10	—	elim.
Longitudinal Analyses	4.48	0.16	28×
Camera Debayering	2.09	0.06	35×
Water Depth	0.13	0.01	13×
Trajectory Parsing [‡]	—	0.02	—
Panoramic Generation [‡]	—	0.15	—
Other [‡]	—	0.41	—
Total	184.03	1.19	155×

[†]Replaced by stream processing (§6);

scanner data now feeds consumers directly.

[‡]Originally external processes (pre-processing steps or separate tools) taking minutes to hours each; now automated by the new pipeline and thus only included in the optimized measurement.

pipeline processes data approximately 60% faster than it is recorded. The Scanner Reading stage, previously the third-largest contributor at 13.1 minutes, was eliminated entirely through the streaming architecture described in §6: scanner data now feeds directly into consumer stages via in-memory callbacks, so its cost is subsumed by the consumer stages it feeds. The Panoramic Generation, Trajectory Parsing, and remaining stages (macrotexture processing, waveband analysis, cross-profile report generation, result aggregation, and database operations) were originally handled by external tools or separate pre-processing steps that each took minutes to hours; in the optimized system, they are fully integrated and complete in a combined 0.58 minutes. Speedup factors vary dramatically across the originally measured stages, reflecting different combinations of the optimization techniques described above. Topographic imaging (499×) benefited from elimination of an external process, SIMD-vectorized hillshading, parallel image generation, and thread-safe WIC encoding. Point cloud processing (399×) benefited from streaming, vectorized coordinate transformation, and the integrated grid-based outlier filter. Longitudinal analysis (28×) benefited primarily from the MATLAB-to-C# migration and SIMD vectorization of the analysis kernels.

Real-time capability and campaign-scale applicability. We verified real-time processing capability on three additional reference datasets of varying length and sensor configuration (recording durations of 447 s,

115s, and 158s). In all cases, processing completed in 57–95% of the recording duration, confirming that the pipeline processes data faster than it is recorded. A full measurement campaign (typically tens or hundreds of kilometers) is composed of hundreds of individual road sections that can be processed independently. Because the pipeline processes each section faster than it was recorded, campaign-scale processing time scales linearly with campaign length, and the real-time guarantee holds regardless of total campaign size. No additional scalability challenges (such as memory pressure or I/O degradation) arise at campaign scale, since each road section is processed in isolation before moving to the next.

11.1. Usability Improvements

While performance was the primary focus, the consolidation and code modernization also yielded usability improvements. The processing application’s user interface no longer blocks during computation. Output files are written to a consistent directory structure, which allows idempotent reprocessing. The entire codebase can be built using a single tool-chain, without manual dependency resolution. Such improvements, while secondary to the performance results, were essential for making the system practical for daily use by field engineers.

11.2. Energy Efficiency

The hardware consolidation also yielded an improvement in energy efficiency. The original eight-server system drew enough power that the servers had to be powered on sequentially to avoid overloading the vehicle’s electrical system. The consolidated single-server system draws approximately one quarter of the power of the original eight servers combined. Combined with the 155× reduction in processing time, the energy consumed per unit of processed data has decreased by roughly two orders of magnitude.

12. LIMITATIONS

An inherent limitation of this case study is that the hardware and software were changed simultaneously. The new server provides approximately 11× the single-threaded performance and 23× the storage bandwidth of the strongest legacy machine (Table 1), so a portion of the 155× speedup is attributable to hardware alone. We did not run the original software on the new hardware (the distributed multi-server architecture would not function on a single machine without significant adaptation), so a controlled ablation separating hardware from software contributions is not viable. However, given that the hardware improvement is approximately one order of magnitude and the total speedup exceeds

two orders of magnitude, we estimate that at least 10–15× of the speedup stems from software and architectural optimizations. The individual per-stage speedups (Table 2) further support this: stages like topographic imaging (499×) and point cloud export (399×) far exceed what hardware improvement alone could explain.

Additionally, all timings reported are single-run measurements without confidence intervals, as the CI benchmark infrastructure recorded one run per commit rather than multiple repetitions. However, as Figure 4 shows, the run-to-run variability is very low (less than 5%).

13. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented the systematic optimization of a real-world, multi-stage LiDAR road assessment pipeline, achieving a 155× end-to-end speedup that enables the system to process data faster than it is recorded. The key insight from this work is that the majority of this improvement came not from novel algorithms, but from the disciplined application of well-known engineering principles to a legacy system that had accumulated over a decade of incremental, heterogeneous development.

The largest single contributor was the elimination of intermediate file I/O through stream processing, which removed entire pipeline stages and tens of gigabytes of temporary storage per measurement. Hardware consolidation from eight distributed servers to a single high-performance node eliminated network transfer overhead and time synchronization complexity, while enabling shared-memory processing that made further optimizations possible. The migration from MATLAB and Python to unified managed C# removed process startup penalties, enabled in-memory data sharing, and provided a single, consistent platform for SIMD vectorization and parallelization. The core numerical kernels, particularly trajectory interpolation, coordinate transformation, and image processing, were vectorized using intrinsics and platform-adaptive vector APIs, yielding per-kernel speedups of 2–8×. Parallelization across the 48 available cores exploited the embarrassingly parallel nature of most pipeline stages.

The continuous, measurement-driven optimization methodology proved essential for navigating the complex interactions between over a dozen pipeline stages. Without CI-integrated benchmarking on reference datasets and per-commit performance tracking, it would have been impractical to identify the dominant bottleneck at each point in the project and to detect regressions early. We believe this profiling-first approach is broadly applicable to other legacy data processing systems where performance has degraded through years of incremental development.

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